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Maximizing Students Understanding in Science through the SOLO Method in Public Schools

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John Biggs and Kevin Collis are known to have developed the SOLO (Structure of Observed Learning Outcomes) Method, which identifies learning outcomes based on their structure. One of the major benefits is that this approach is knowledge-based and different from the conventional approaches to learning that mostly rely on memory rather than understanding and the capability to apply the results of such knowledge in practice.

This is helpful in teaching-learning, more so in science, where learners are required to master concepts. Biggs and Collis (1982) have explained that using the taxonomy of learning, the development of a learner's understanding of a subject from surface to deep learning can be described systematically (*SOLO Taxonomy | John Biggs, 2019*).

The SOLO Method categorizes learning into five levels: namely, pre-structural, uni-structural, multi-structural, relational, and extended abstract. At the pre-structural level, students have minimal to no notion regarding the subject. At the uni-structural and multi-structural levels, they can list or describe what particular concept they know about.

Nevertheless, at the relational level, students can establish relationships between these concepts and hence arrive at an integrated impression. Lastly, at the extended abstract level, students can show how their knowledge can be applied to other situations and situations they have not encountered before (*Structural Learning, 2022*).

According to "Classteaching", the method used in a science classroom can be exemplified by the tactics considered in the following sub-sections. For instance, teachers can establish lessons that require learners to go from stating facts within a given science domain (multi-structural) to explaining how these facts are interrelated (relational). An example could be a lab experiment where you add two chemicals together and students not only see the reaction but can also discuss why the reaction occurs and what will occur if this or that is modified. It also enables students to move from surface learning to deep learning, which enhances their understanding of scientific concepts (*Classteaching, 2014*).

Furthermore, the SOLO Method complements the formative assessment practices effectively. The use of SOLO-based rubrics is beneficial for teachers because they are able to give more specific feedback to students as well as assist the student in identifying the level at which they are currently operating and what is required for them to operate at a higher level. Such feedback is more effective in terms of education than standard letter grades and can greatly improve the results for the students (*Structural Learning, 2022b*).

In terms of specific teaching strategies, the SOLO Method provides a solid basis for improving students' learning in science. First, highlighting the difficulty of the learning outcomes

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allows for a better understanding of the content and, for the student, builds the capacity of how to apply what has been learned across different situations.

As it is seen, besides consolidating conceptual knowledge, this method enhances the abilities of critical thinking and problem solving—the skills crucial for success in the sciences and other spheres of life as well. In this pursuit of the goal for educators to find the best ways of teaching science, a method that seems to provide learning is the SOLO Method.

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